

Economic Analysis

Energy conversion of ratoon rice and its financial benefits

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Double-cropped rice does not fit well in southeast Sichuan because of low temperatures. How to increase food production in the limited cultivated land of the municipality with the largest population in China is a problem.

Ratoon rice production is developing rapidly with wide adoption of Shanyou 63, a hybrid rice with good ratooning

ability and medium duration. The area of ratoon rice cropping, 670 ha in 1986, reached 1.9 million ha in 1989. Production increase with ratoon rice was 5.8 million t in 4 yr. The main pattern for irrigated rice cropping systems in Chongqing is now rice - ratoon rice (or wheat, rape, and barley after ratoon rice harvest).

We evaluated energy conversion, grain yield, and financial benefits of several rice-based cropping systems 1987-89. Labor inputs were derived from a survey of 100 farmers. Financial analysis was based on the state purchasing price.

One season cropping of rice has the lowest energy input and output (Table 1).

Energy output from rice - ratoon rice is 56.7 billion J/ha higher; energy input, 12.4 billion J/ha higher.

Because land use is prolonged with ratoon cropping, sunlight use efficiency/year of a field also increased.

Ratoon rice costs less to grow than wheat or rape (Table 2). Total output value and net output value/\$ invested are higher in the cropping systems with ratoon rice. Labor productivity of rice - ratoon rice is a little lower than that of one crop of rice.

We estimate the rice production from 2.0 million ha of ricefields could increase as much as 4.5 million t, if ratoon rice yields are a conservative 2.2 t/ha. ■

Table 1. Energy conversion for cropping systems in Chongqing ricefields, China.

	Energy conversion factor ^a (x1 million J)	Rice		Rice - ratoon rice		Wheat - rice		Wheat-rice-ratoon rice		Rape - rice		Rape - rice - ratoon rice	
		Quantity /ha	Billion J/ha	Quantity /ha	Billion J/ha	Quantity /ha	Billion J/ha	Quantity ha	Billion J/ha	Quantity /ha	Billion J/ha	Quantity /ha	Billion J/ha
Input			46.4		58.8		94.4		106.1		97.9		107.1
Organic ^b			34.1		40.2		70.7		75.1		76.5		77.1
Labor	0.75	2340 h	1.76	2940 h	2.21	5112 h	3.83	5712 h	4.28	6384 h	4.79	6984 h	5.24
Seeds ^c		112.5 kg	1.70	112.5 kg	1.70	240 kg	3.77	240 kg	3.77	122.3 kg	1.87	122.3 kg	1.87
Compost (dry matter)	13.5	2270 kg	30.64	2688 kg	36.29	4674 kg	63.1	4966 kg	67.05	5173 kg	69.84	5184 kg	69.99
Inorganic ^d			12.3		18.6		23.7		31.0		21.4		30.0
Nitrogen	90.0	105.4 kg	9.59	172 kg	15.65	189 kg	17.20	274.5 kg	24.98	169.8 kg	15.45	260 kg	23.66
Phosphorus	13.3	27.0 kg	0.36	31.5 kg	0.42	79.5 kg	1.06	84.0 kg	1.12	81.75 kg	1.09	86.25 kg	1.15
Potassium	9.0	30.15 kg	0.27	36 kg	0.32	60 kg	0.54	64.5 kg	0.58	63.0 kg	0.57	64.65 kg	0.58
Tools	210.0	7.43 kg	1.56	7.71 kg	1.62	12.43 kg	2.61	13.67 kg	2.87	13.0 kg	2.73	13.80 kg	2.90
Insecticides and herbicides	102.0	5.1 kg	0.52	5.78 kg	0.59	13.1 kg	1.34	14.2 kg	1.45	15.3 kg	1.56	16.76 kg	1.71
Output			233.7		290.4		314.9		353.9		326.0		365.0
Grain			122.1		151.8		159.8		180.2		148.8		170.5
Straw			111.6		138.6		155.1		113.7		177.2		194.5
Total energy output/input			5.04		4.94		3.34		3.34		3.33		3.41
Sunlight use efficiency			.73%		.97%		1.05%		1.18%		1.09%		1.22%

^aEnergy conversion factors are from Gou Xiaohong, Du Hongzuo (1989) A preliminary approach to energy flow in Chongqing agro-ecosystem. J. Southwest Agric. Univ. 11(3):319-324. ^bOrganic energy does not include animal power in no-till ricefield. ^cEnergy conversion factors of seeds of rice, wheat, and rape are 15.1 million J/kg, 16.3 million J/kg, 2.63 million J/kg. ^dEnergy of film used to cover seedlings is too little to be counted.

Table 2. Grain yield and financial benefits from cropping systems in Chongqing ricefields, China.

Cropping system	Grain yield (t/ha)				Total value (\$/ha)	Total cost (\$/ha)	Net value (\$/ha)	Net value/\$ infested	Labor productivity (\$/d)
	Rice	Ratoon rice	Wheat	Rape					
Rice	8.1				920	398	522	1.31	3.15
Rice - ratoon rice	8.1	2.0			1144	468	676	1.44	3.11
Wheat - rice	7.6		2.7		1250	746	504	0.68	1.96
Wheat - rice - ratoon rice	7.6	1.4	2.7		1404	816	588	0.72	1.97
Rape - medium rice	8.1			1.6	1462	832	631	0.76	1.83
Rape - rice - ratoon rice	8.1	1.4		1.6	1626	902	724	0.80	1.86

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.